

THE EFFECT OF LAMINATE CONFIGURATION ON DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF CFRP COMPOSITE BEAM SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of flexural loading on damage characteristics and residual compressive strength (RCS) of graphite/epoxy specimens was investigated. The purpose of this study was to develop a laboratory-scale methodology for damage tolerance evaluation for composite laminates. The following parametric effects were investigated: layer stacking sequence, laminate thickness, boundary conditions etc. Failure modes and mechanisms were related to the respective state of stress and damage characteristics. It was concluded that shear delamination mechanism, which prevails mainly in the case of clamped short beams, is the most significant mode affecting RCS degradation. On the other hand, edge-delamination process, which was found to be predominant in the case of long simply-supported beams, seems to have a relatively small effect on RCS.

Laminate compressive failure process was mainly controlled by sub-laminate buckling. It was found to be affected by delamination length, its location and by sub-laminate lay-up. The thickness of the individual layers (roughness and distribution) was also found to have significant effect on damage characteristics and RCS degradation.

Discussion of test findings in the light of previous studies on interlaminar fracture toughness (IFT) lead to the conclusion that the interrelationship between flexural moment (energy), damage characteristics and RCS, as derived from beam specimen testing may provide a sensitive tool for comparative damage tolerance evaluation of different composite material systems.

INTRODUCTION

In most cases, structural composite materials are designed to withstand inplane loading. However, under service and maintenance real conditions, these materials are liable to be exposed to lateral loading, which usually is applied perpendicular to the external surface of the structure. In such cases, the composite laminate is flexurally loaded. Such loading may induce anisotropic moment distribution due to boundary conditions. Hence, beam model may represent a significant extreme case of lateral flexural loading of plates. Generally, the external load which is responsible for the damage may be applied abruptly as impact and could be imposed slowly in a quasi-static way.

The investigation presently reported is concerned with the effect of initial flexural loading on damage characteristics and its consequent effects on residual compressive strength (RCS) which is considered to be the dominant and most sensitive property affected by the presence of interlaminar damages (delaminations).

The interrelationship between initial impact energy and RCS is considered to be the main quantitative function for damage tolerance evaluation. It is commonly defined as compressive strength after impact and serves mainly for comparative assessment of different candidate composite material systems designated for structural elements in the aircraft industry.

The main advantage of the present procedure, which is involved with quasi-static loading of beam specimens, is by the ability to follow up on-line the failure process as a function of the loading

sequence. In such a way the initial formation and growth of flaws and delamination could be detected optically and failure mechanisms could be related to respective states of stress prevailing within the internal structure of the composite laminate.

TEST VARIABLES

In all cases the relationship between initial flexural load (IFL) (moment or energy) and residual compressive strength were derived and studied. The relevant test variables were: initial flexural loading level - normal and shear stress components at different levels of damage process - namely: transverse matrix cracking, edge delamination and shear delamination; damage characteristics: size of delaminations, their location and distribution; compressive loading levels - as related to the different stage of delamination growth, sublaminates buckling and ultimate compressive fracture.

The effect of the following parameters on RCS vs. IFL relationship was investigated:

- (a) Different layer stacking sequence: $(\pm 45/90/0)_{sn}$ vs. $(\pm 45/0/90)_{sn}$.
- (b) The effect of layer distribution - fine array $[(\pm 45/0/90)_{sn}]_2$ vs. rough array $(\pm 45_s/0_2/90_2)_{sn}$.
- (c) The effect of laminate thickness - 32 layers vs. 48 layers.
- (d) The effect of a boundary condition - freely supported beams vs. clamped beam.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1. Material and Specimens

Beam specimens were prepared from AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy laminates composed of 32 and 48 layers stacked in quasi-isotropic array (about 4.1 mm and 6.4 mm thickness respectively). In most cases, specimens of about 8 mm width and 70 mm length were cut from the laminate by means of a diamond coated high-speed saw disc. Generally, three basic laminates were used having the following layer stacking sequences:

- Laminate A: $(+45/-45/0/90)_{s4}$ (32 layers)
Laminate B: $(\pm 45_s/0_2/90_2)_{s2}$ (32 layers)
Laminate C: $(+45/-45/0/90)_{s6}$ (48 layers)

The beams were cut in two perpendicular directions to the laminate thus comprising of 6 different stacking sequences.

2. Test Procedure

Before loading, the specimens were coated with white brittle paint on the front side on which marks of 5 mm scale were drawn. Such coating was found to be crack sensitive and served to visualize the damage pattern on external surfaces. Two test stages were conducted as follows:

(a) The beams (having 60 mm span in most cases) were loaded in a 3 point loading fixture by means of an Instron tester at a constant cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. In most cases, the loading procedure was followed up by video-acoustic set-up which enables the amplified detection of different failure processes. By such means the initiation and growth of transverse cracking, edge delamination and shear delamination could be directly detected and recorded for further examination. At different load levels, the specimens were unloaded and later transferred to the compressive loading fixture.

(b) Compressive loading was conducted similarly to ASTM D695 standard. A constant cross-head speed of 1 mm/min was maintained. Specimens were loaded in compression up to the ultimate fracture level. Tests were monitored and amplified by video inspection techniques.

During stage (a), delamination of different sizes and locations were formed and propagated as a function of flexure loading, whereas at stage (b) the effect of such delamination on residual compressive strength was evaluated.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Damage Process

Two types of failure modes were observed during flexural loading at stage (a), namely:

(1) Edge delamination which was formed at the first 90° layers within the tensile zone of the simply-supported beams. Such delamination initiated at the middle of the span under a relatively low loading level and propagated slowly from the middle towards the supports as a function of the flexural moment.

(2) Shear delamination was formed abruptly to their full length at locations closer to midplane of clamped beams. At relatively lower loading levels only 1-2 cracks were formed. Increasing loading levels induced additional shear delamination, which in turn caused significant reduction of beam stiffness (Fig. 1).

Under subsequent compressive loading of previously damaged specimens at shear delamination mode, three basic damage-growth mechanisms were observed (Fig. 2):

- (a) Delamination opening.
- (b) Single sublaminar buckling.
- (c) Successive multi-sublaminar buckling process terminated by ultimate compressive fracture of the composite.

2. The Effect of Initial Flexural Loading

IFL seems to have only a slight effect on RCS up to a critical level beyond which a significant reduction of RCS is evident (Figs. 3,4). This critical level can be defined as a level of strength degradation. Such a level could be measured in terms of load, moment or energy. IFL has a roughly linear effect on the increase of edge-delamination length (EDL) in the case of simply-supported beams having $\pm 45^\circ$ layer at the external surfaces (Fig. 5).

3. The Effect of Edge-Delamination Length

In tests conducted by flexure of simply-supported beams, edge delamination was the predominant damage mechanism as expected. Such a delamination was formed and propagated along the 90° layer closest to the external $\pm 45^\circ$ layers. Hence, in the case of sequence $(\pm 45_s/0_2/90_2)_{s2}$ the separated sublaminar was $(0_2/\pm 45_2)$ which has a more significant effect on stiffness and RCS reduction than that compared with the case of sequence $(\pm 45_s/90_2/0_2)_{s2}$ where the separate sublaminar consisted of $(\pm 45_2)$ layers alone. This trend is shown in Fig. 2. A similar trend can be found when comparing fine layer distribution with its rough counterpart (see Fig. 3). In all the above cases only slight effect of EDL on RCS reduction was found, as shown in Fig. 6.

4. The Effect of the Layers Stacking Sequence and Laminar Thickness

Layers at which tensile stresses are acting transverse to fiber orientation are the most sensitive to matrix and interfacial cracking, becoming the weak-link of the laminar, where interlaminar damage is liable to propagate. Hence, under uniaxial flexural loading the 90° layers determines the location of the interlaminar damage formation, and is critical to the ultimate failure of the laminar under subsequent compressive loading. In cases where edge-delamination is the prevailing mechanism, it was found that reduction rate of RCS increase with the distance of the first 90° layer from the external tensile surface. Hence, in the case of $(\pm 45/90/0)_{sn}$, edge delamination has insignificant effect on RCS as compared with $(\pm 45_s/0_2/90_2)_{sn}$. In cases where shear delamination mechanism prevails (clamped beams) damage is located closer to beam midplane, and a single sublaminar buckling under subsequent compressive loading is not the predominant mechanism which effect RCS. Here, ultimate compressive fracture is controlled by delamination propagation and eventually by multi-sublaminar buckling. In this case, the location of a 90° layer is less critical than its thickness and rough layer distribution is worse than its fine counterpart.

Another factor which may affect the criticality of interlaminar damage to RCS is the ratio between the thickness of the separated sublaminar to the overall laminar thickness. Following this consideration, thinner laminates are expected to be more sensitive to interlaminar damage than

thicker ones, provided other composition parameters are the same. The lay-up of the major part of the laminate after separation of an external sublaminar is also an important factor. If such a lay-up will be non-symmetrical, the deleterious effect of the separation will be much more severe than if compared with the case of symmetrical lay-up. Hence, from damage tolerance consideration the four lay-ups in the present study may be graded in the following order:

Best $\rightarrow (\pm 45/90/0)_{s4} \rightarrow (\pm 45_s/90_2/0_2)_{s2} \rightarrow (\pm 45/90/0)_{s4} \rightarrow (\pm 45_s/90_2/0_2)_{s2} \rightarrow$ worst

This trend is supported by the present experimental findings.

5. The Effect of Specimen Span and Boundary Conditions

At the initial flexure loading stage, two types of boundary conditions were compared - free supports vs. clamped edges. The tests were conducted on beams having a short span (60 mm) compared with those with a long span (80 mm). In the case of long beams in simply-supported conditions, the mechanism of edge delamination prevailed and had a relatively small effect on RCS degradation. In the case of long beams with clamped edges, a mixed damage pattern was detected comprising of short edge delaminations and long shear delaminations starting from the middle of the beam. The ratio between shear and normal stresses in a beam depends on its span to thickness ratio and on boundary conditions. Hence, in the case of simply-supported long beams where tensile stresses prevail, edge delamination mechanics become predominant. Clamping will increase shear to normal stress ratio, and may increase the chances for shear delamination damage. Accordingly, shear delamination will be the prevailing damage mechanism in the case of clamped short beams, as was demonstrated in the experimental findings. Comparison of RCS vs. IFL relationship for clamped edges vs. simply-supported beams of the same composition and size will show far better performances for the clamped condition. However, this is not a fair comparison. A more adequate approach would be to relate RCS to initial flexural energy. Such a relationship would show similar trends for simply-supported and clamped conditions with still higher RCS levels for the clamped specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental and analytical results of tests conducted on quasi-isotropic CFRP beam specimens which were damaged under flexure and loaded to ultimate fracture in compression lead to the following conclusions:

- (1) Edge delamination damage was the prevailing mechanism in most cases of simply-supported beams under initial flexural loading. It occurred at the tensile zone, close to the external surface.
- (2) Shear delamination damage was the prevailing mechanism in the case of clamped specimens, it initiated frequently in the tensile zone at about 1/4 of the thickness and propagated abruptly into a multi-delamination pattern with increasing load.
- (3) Edge delamination had a small effect on residual compressive strength reduction compared with a higher effect found due to shear delamination.
- (4) Laminated beams having fine lay-up distribution are characterized by better damage tolerance performance as compared with rough counterparts.
- (5) The distance of 90° and 0° layers from the tensile beam surface affects damage tolerance performance. From this viewpoint, layer stacking sequence of $(\pm 45/90/0)_{sn}$ are better than $(\pm 45/0/90)_{sn}$ counterparts.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1: Typical shear-delamination damage formed under flexure of clamped beams (Stage A), showing single shear-delamination at initial loading level (a) and multi-shear delaminations at high loading level (b).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 2: Typical shear-delamination growth process under compressive loading of clamped specimens
 (a) delamination crack opening
 (b) delamination crack propagation and single sub-laminate buckling
 (c) multi-sub-laminate buckling - ultimate failure process.

Fig. 3: The effect of initial flexural moment on residual compressive strength (RCS) of CFRP quasi-isotropic specimens.

- △ Simply supported ($\pm 45_s / 90_2 / 0_2$)_{s2} beams
- Simply supported ($\pm 45_s / 0_2 / 90_2$)_{s2} beams

Fig. 4: The effect of initial flexural moment on residual compressive strength (RCS) of CFRP quasi-isotropic specimens.

- Simply supported ($\pm 45/90/0$)_{s4} beams
- Simply supported ($\pm 45_s / 0_2 / 90_2$)_{s2} beams

Fig. 5: The effect of initial flexural load on edge delamination length in CFRP ($\pm 45_s / 90_2 / 0_2$)_{s2} beams.

Fig. 6: The effect of edge delamination length on residual compressive strength of CFRP quasi-isotropic specimens.

- Simply supported ($\pm 45/90/0$)_{s4} beams
- Simply supported ($\pm 45_s / 0_2 / 90_2$)_{s2} beams

* Flexural moment for initiation-of RCS degradation.